

An Investigation on Perception of Teaching Practice Exercise among Mathematics Education Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

Ekpenyong, Effiong Ibok¹

ibokekpenyong@yahoo.com

08063923224

Ogar, Raymong Ogbebe²

Raymond20ogar@gmail.com

07039437156

Obogo, Emmanuel Joseph³

obogoemmanuel@gmail.com

08065820074

Unoh, Edet Okon⁴

unohedet@gmail.com

08020683635

¹Department of Science Education, Faculty of Vocational & Science Education. University of Calabar, Cross River State.

²Department of Special Education, Faculty of Education Foundational Studies. University of Calabar, Cross River State.

³Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Physical Sciences. University of Cross River State, Calabar

⁴Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education. University of Calabar, Cross River State.

Abstract

This study adopted descriptive survey research design to investigate the perception of teaching practice exercise among Mathematics education students in public University in Cross river State, Nigeria. It was guided by two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The population of 410 (195 male and 215 female) final year final year science education students during the 2021/2022 academic year in both University of Calabar and Cross River State University who were selected through census approach were used sample for the study. One instrument titled “Perception on teaching practices Questionnaire (PTPQ) was employed to gather the data. The reliability of questionnaire using Cronbach Alpha method yielded 0.89. The first hypotheses were tested using population t-test and the second null hypothesis was were tested using the independent t -test for hypothesis two inferential analysis. Both were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed there is significant difference in the perception of Mathematics student-teacher on the practice exercise and there was a significant difference in male and female Mathematics student-teacher perception toward teaching practice exercise in public universities in Cross River State. it was concluded that student teacher perception influences in their involvement and interest in teaching practice exercise. Based on the conclusion of this study, it was recommended, amongst others, that workshops, conferences and seminars should be organised regularly for student - teacher to sustain and or maintain the high level of interest and motivation toward teaching practice exercise they claimed to have.

Keywords: Student-teacher, teaching practices, Mathematics Education, gender

Introduction

Mathematics is a core subject in most educational systems, and its importance cannot be overemphasized. Mathematics provides students with problem-solving skills, logical thinking, and analytical skills that are essential for success in various fields. Every individual needs the knowledge of Mathematics to function intelligently and efficiently because the subject is an integral part of the human life (Ibok, Meremikwu, & Umoh, 2020). There is virtually no discipline one can think of which does not require Mathematics or have inputs from Mathematics. It is important for prospective math teachers to engage in teaching practice exercises (Ibok, Thomas, & Nyong, 2019). Nonetheless, it doesn't appear like a very good impression of the crucial teaching methods exercise was given to the student-teachers of mathematics during their training. Their perspective on the activity deviates from the goal for which it was intended. They usually approach the practice with amusement and a

An Investigation on Perception of Teac ... (Ekpenyong et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737742>

lukewarm attitude. Their behavior throughout the teaching practice exercise appeared to be a combination of cooperation and insincerity. This had an impact on the program's proper execution and explains why there are currently too few high-quality math teachers in our educational institutions (Ibok & Unoh, 2019). A key component of professional mathematics teachers' training is teaching practice exercises. For a vocation to be considered perfect, it must possess certain attributes and characteristics. Across the globe, teaching is regarded as one of the primary occupations. As a result, it is crucial that it fulfill the prerequisites for a vocation. In addition to offering social services, having professional ethics, and having the freedom to work, it is essential that aspiring professional teachers have both theoretical and practical training. The goal of this is to introduce the students to the necessary practical side of their chosen field of study. The aspiring professional educators are equipped with the fundamental resources necessary to meet the demands of their line of work. According to Parr et al. (2021), teaching is the process by which a person who is thought to be more educated imparts knowledge to students.

During the teaching practice phase of their apprenticeship, pre-service teachers can use the skills they have learned in the classroom. During this internship, a variety of theoretical pedagogical skills are implemented in real-world settings. It offers student teachers the chance to apply what they have learned in the classroom. They have direct interactions with the pupils, the course materials, and the educational setting. Pre-service teachers benefit from this by having the chance to expand their knowledge and skill sets as well as learn new ideas, approaches, and strategies for the real classroom and teaching in general. The goal of teaching practice is to develop successful, purposeful, and effective teachers who will in turn develop successful citizens in the future.

The teaching process gives the students the chance to grow personally in terms of their professional competencies, knowledge, comprehension, abilities, and pedagogical ideals. But Goller et al. (2019) provided the following summary of the goals of instructional practice:

i) giving students the chance to put theory into practice; ii) providing real-world experience, chances, and resources to help them become more confident and knowledgeable; iii) giving them the capacity to plan, direct, and oversee a classroom with appropriate disciplinary measures; iv) developing a global and mutual sense of cooperation as well as the exchange of ideas and attitudes. According to Escribano and Hervis (2018), there exists a high correlation between the caliber of teachers and the caliber of educational systems. This makes it more difficult for new teachers to receive their training and emphasizes the necessity to find student teachers who are highly motivated to teach. The view of the reasons behind pursuing a teaching career has generally been linked to prospective teachers' professional work performance and persistence (Abós et al., 2018; Muñoz-Fernández et al., 2019; Watt & Richardson, 2020). Research indicates that educators who perceive their students' motives highly are more dedicated to their students' learning and professional growth (García-Poyato et al., 2018; Goller et al., 2019; Watt et al., 2017). According to Abós et al. (2018), there is universal consensus that student-teachers who exhibit higher levels of professional commitment, lower levels of burnout, and extraordinary adherence to teaching techniques are the most motivated. In fact, there is evidence linking student teacher perception to professional burnout, teacher optimism, and feelings like delight or anxiety (McLean et al., 2019; Parr et al., 2021). Under this situation, knowing how student teachers view becoming teachers and growing as future educators will assist shape policies that draw in quality educators (Han & Yin, 2016). Additionally, it permits the consideration of how to more effectively support student-teachers during their formative years and as they enter the teaching profession (Tardif & Tremblay-Gagnon, 2021).

However, there isn't much research examining the impact of demographic factors like age, socioeconomic status, and sex on teaching practices in the empirical studies currently available on students' and teachers' perceptions of those practices (Alexander et al., 2020; Stolk et al., 2021; Watt et al., 2017). Variations in the traits, dispositions, and skills of male and female student-teachers may have an impact on their willingness to actively engage in instructional activities (Ibok, et al., 2022).. In their research, Klassen et al. (2011) discovered that gender roles had a major impact on Omani people's decisions to become teachers, but not Canadian people. Azman (2013) conducted a study in Malaysia which revealed that gender-based teaching approaches have a notable positive impact on female pupils. According to Butt et al. (2010), female may also choose teaching as a career due to their perceptions in terms of the desire to acquire new skills and knowledge, and the desire to balance work and family obligations. Conversely, men decide to become teachers for more external factors, including vacations, social lives, or financial security (Alpaslan & Damli, 2022; Balyer & Özcan, 2014; Struyven et al., 2013). In a study, Elacqua et al. (2018) discovered that gender is a crucial factor influencing a person's willingness to pursue a career in teaching. In this context, new research by (Akar, 2019; Akpochafo, 2020) has revealed that choosing to become a teacher is influenced significantly by one's gender. It is true that the objectives and perspectives of male and female student-teachers about instructional techniques differ (Eghtesadi- Roudi, 2021; Gratacós & López-Jurado, 2016). In their study, Bhana and Moosa (2016) discovered that male and female students have different motivations for selecting teaching as a career. Therefore, it is the duty of both pre-service

An Investigation on Perception of Teac ... (Ekpenyong et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737742>

teachers and teacher educators to prepare students for teaching practice. It is the responsibility of teacher educators to set up appropriate learning materials, instructional strategies, and assessment procedures to get their pupils ready for this kind of program. Enough exposure of the pupils to courses that will improve their on-field performance is required. As important as professional development for educators is in producing qualified instructors, pupils' attitudes about self-adequate preparation for upcoming tasks are equally important. One of the main components of their professional training is teaching practice exercises, for which the students must be ready. In addition to personally preparing for the exercise, they must submit to the instruction and direction of their educators.

Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study is to investigate the perception of teaching practice exercise among mathematics education students in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seek to examined

- i) The level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise in Cross River State
- ii) The difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise in Cross River State

Research questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

- i) What are the level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise?
- ii) What are the difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested, at 0.05 significant level, to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between perception of Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between perception of male and female Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State.

Methodology

The research area was public Universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was used adopted for this study. The researchers used this design because the researchers were able to draw large sample of student-teacher in their various institutions, described, examined their perception and gender difference toward teaching practices exercises. The population for the study consisted of all the 410 final year students in science Mathematics education Department in public Universities in Cross River State (University of Calabar and Cross River State University) were used for the study. A sample of 410(195 male and 215 female) science education students during 2021/2022 academic year were selected via Census approach. Census sampling was used because the population is small enough to handle by the researchers for the study. The break down of the sample shows that 298 students were selected from University of Calabar while 112 were selected from Cross River State University.

One instrument was used for data collection titled “perception of teaching practices Questionnaire”. Parts A and B made up the questionnaire. Part A needed information on students' demographic data such as sex; while section B was consisted of 20 items to test students' perception on teaching practice exercise. The instrument was based on four-point Likert Scale of strongly agreed which was scored 4 points, agreed scored 3 points, disagreed scored 2 points, and strongly disagreed scored 1 point. The questionnaire items were developed by the researchers and was face-validated by two experts in both Measurement and Evaluation and Science Educators in the University of Calabar. Corrections were pointed up by the experts and adjusted by the researchers and the document was considered legitimate or valid. The reliability of the questionnaire was established using 50 final year students in public Universities in Akwa Ibom State who were not part of the main study but however shared similar characteristic with the study population. After the trial test, Cronbach Alpha method was used and the internal consistency estimates which gives 0.89. These were adjudged high and guaranteed the use of the instrument for the research. Since the reliability index is above 0.50, the estimates were considered high enough for the study. The Statistics Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer programme was used to analyze the data collected. Research questions were answer using descriptive statistics. The hypothesis one was tested using population t-test while hypothesis two was tested with independent t-test.

An Investigation on Perception of Teac ... (Ekpenyong et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737742>

Results

The result of the analysis is presented in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions while population t test and independent t-test were used to test the null hypotheses at .05 significant level.

Research question one

The level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise. To provide answers to this research question, overall expected mean and observed mean of the 20 items constructed were compared and the result is presented in table 1

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise.

Variable name	Number of items	Expected mean	Observed mean	Decision
Perception of teaching practice	20	50.000	53.621	Agreed

Sources; Field work, 2023

The result from table 1 showed that the overall observed mean of 53,621 was higher than the expected mean of 50.000 which agreed with the high level of Mathematics education student-teacher perception toward involvement in teaching practice exercise.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between perception of Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State..

For the Mathematics education student-teacher perception on disposed to teaching practice exercise to be significantly in public Universities in Cross River State, the score on perception of disposed to teaching practice exercise should be significantly greater than 50.0 which is the expected average for the perception on disposed to teaching practice exercise. This hypothesis was tested with a test of one sample mean (population t-test) and the result is shown in table 1

Table 2: Population t -test analysis on the extent of Mathematics education student-teacher perception on involvement in teaching practice exercises(N= 410)

Expected mean=50.0

Variable	Observed mean	Mean error	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision
Perception of teaching practices	53.621	0.211	4.267	1.161	.000	Significant

*Significant at the .05 level, df =409, t-critical =1.96

Sources; Field work, 2023

The information in table 2 also revealed the computation t-value of 17.161 associated with p-value of .000 at .05 level of significant shows that there is a significant difference in the mathematics education student- teacher perception on involvement teaching practice exercise .. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Research question two

What are the difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise?

To answer this research question, descriptive statistics was employed, and the result presented in Table 3

Table 3: Mean of perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise (N=410)

Gender	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Decision
Male	195	48.17	11.23	Agreed
Female	215	59.40		

Sources; Field work, 2023

An Investigation on Perception of Teac ... (Ekpenyong et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737742>

The results presented in Table 1 reveals that the mean score of female Mathematics student teacher toward teaching practice exercise was (59.40) which higher than their male counterpart with mean score (48.17) which implies that there is a difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers toward teaching practice exercise with favour of female student teacher. Female student- teacher with the mean score of 59.40 have more positive perception on involvement in teaching practice than their male counterpart with mean score of 48.17.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers to teaching practice exercise in tertiary institution in Cross River State.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is gender while the dependent variable is student –teacher perception on teacher practices . In testing this hypothesis, the mean scores of the male and female education student teacher perception to teaching practice exercise in public universities in Cross River State their mean, standard deviation were computed and compared using independent t-test and the results is shown in table 4.

Table 4: Results of independent t - test analysis of the significant difference between perception of male and female Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State(N=410)

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision
Perception of teaching practice	Male	195	48.17	4.889	22.591	.000	Significant
	Female	215	59.40	5.173			
	Total	410	50.56	4.267			

*Significant at the .05 level, t-critical =1.96, df =408

Sources; Field work, 2023

The result presented on Table 4 shows that the t value of 22.591 associated with p value of .000 shows that there is a significant difference in the perception of male and female Mathematics education student-teachers to teaching practice exercise in tertiary institution in Cross River State.. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected at the 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of findings

The result of hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant difference in perception of Mathematics students on teaching practice exercise in Cross River State..in public University in Cross River State. This is in line with Escribano and Hervis, (2018) who noted that the quality of educational systems is closely connected with the quality of its professors. The finding concurred with García-Poyato et al., (2018); Goller et al., (2019); Watt et al., (2017) who stated that student –teacher with high perception of motives are more devoted to their professional development. According to Abós et al. (2018), there is universal consensus that student-teachers who exhibit higher levels of professional commitment, lower levels of burnout, and extraordinary adherence to teaching techniques are the most motivated. The finding is in line with Han and Yin, (2016) who found that student-teacher perception on involvement in teaching practice exercise to be significantly high

The result of hypothesis two revealed that there is significant influence of gender on Mathematics education student-teachers perception on involvement of teaching practice exercise in Public Universities in Cross River State. The finding is in line with Ibok, et al.,(2022) who see differences in characteristics, attitudes, and abilities of male and female student- teacher who could influence their active participation in teaching practices. This is in line with Fray and Gore, (2018) who found gender influencing the decision to teach or teaching practices The finding agreed with the finding of Klassen et al. (2011) who discovered that gender roles strongly influenced choosing teaching as a vocation. Conversely, men decide to become teachers for more external factors, including vacations, social lives, or financial security (Alpaslan & Damli, 2022; Balyer & Özcan, 2014; Struyven et al., 2013).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded from this study that there was significance difference in perception of mathematics education student-teacher on involvement in teaching practice exercise.. However, female students have more positive perception toward involvement of exercise exercises than their male counterpart in students in public universities. Therefore, students' positive perception and gender are important factors to considered by educational

An Investigation on Perception of Teac ... (Ekpenyong et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737742>

authorities among other strategies to promote and motivate students' in involvement in teaching practices exercises in Cross river state any tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this investigation, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Mathematics education students should be better directed as to the relevance of teaching practice exercise to their preparation as prospective professional teachers.
- 2) More information about the necessity to alter one's perspective and adopt a positive attitude about the activity should be provided to male education students. They would eventually be able to use their pedagogical abilities on the field more effectively and learn more from the program as a result.

References

- Abós, Á., Haerens, L., Sevil, J., Aelterman, N., & García-González, L. (2018). Teachers' motivation in relation to their psychological functioning and interpersonal style: A variable- and person-centered approach. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 74, 21–34.
- Akar, E. O. (2019). Alternative teacher certification students' motivations of teaching. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education (Online)*, 44(1), 71-81
- Akpochafo, G. O. (2020). Motivation for pre-service students to choose a teaching career by gender, age, and subject area in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(2) 289–297.
- Alexander, C., Wyatt-Smith, C., & Du Plessis, A. (2020). The role of motivations and perceptions on the retention of in-service teachers. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 96, 103186. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103186>
- Alpaslan, M. M., & Damli, N. (2022). Relations of in-service science teachers' career motivation with demographic variables. *Online Science Education Journal*, 7(1), 28–38.
- Bakar, A., Shamsiah, M., Asmawati, S., & Ramlah, H. (2014). So you want to be a teacher: What are your reasons? *International Education Studies Archives*, 7(11), 155–161.
- Balyer, A., & Özcan, K. (2014). Choosing teaching profession as a career: Students' reasons. *International Education Studies*, 7(5), 104–115.
- Bhana, D., & Moosa, S. (2016). Failing to attract males in foundation phase teaching: An issue of masculinities. *Gender and Education*, 28(1), 1–19.
- Butt, G., MacKenzie, L., & Manning, R. (2010). Influences on British South Asian women's choice of teaching as a career: "You're either a career person or a family person; teaching kind of fits in the middle". *Educational Review*, 62(1), 69–83.
- Consejo Nacional de Educación (CNEC). (2021) Informe de tendencias de la matrícula de pregrado en la educación superior. [Higher education undergraduate enrolment trends report]. https://www.cned.cl/sites/default/files/02_informepregrado2021_final.pdf
- Eghtesadi Roudi, A. (2021). Why to become a teacher in Iran: A FIT-Choice study. *Teaching Education*, 1(1) 1–20.
- Elacqua, G., Hincapié, D., Vegas, E., Alfonso, M., Montalva, V., & Paredes, D. (2018). Why has teaching prestige been lost and how to recover it?. Inter-American Development Bank. <http://doi.org/10.18235/0001172>
- Escribano-Hervis, E. (2018). Teacher performance as a factor associated with educational quality in Latin America. *Revista Educación*, 42(2), 717–739.
- Fray, L., & Gore, J. (2018). Why people choose teaching: A scoping review of empirical studies, 2007–2016. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 75, 153–163.
- García-Poyato, J., Cordero Arroyo, G., & Torres Hernández, R. M. (2018).: A review of empirical studies published in the 21st century. *Perspectiva Educativa*, 57(2), 51–72.
- Goller, M., Ursin, J., Vähäsantanen, K., Festner, D., & Harteis, C. (2019). Finnish and German student teachers' motivations for choosing teaching as a career: The first application of the FIT-Choice Scale in Finland. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85, 235–248.
- Gratacós, G., & López-Jurado, M. (2016). Validation of the Spanish version of the Factors Influencing Teaching (FIT) Choice Scale. *Revista de Educación*, 272, 83–105.

An Investigation on Perception of Teac ... (Ekpenyong et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737742>

- Gratacós, G., López-Gómez, E., Nocito, G., & Sastre, S. (2017). *Why teach?* Antecedents and consequences in Spain. In H. M. G. Watt, K. Smith, & P. W. Richardson (Eds.), *Global perspectives on teacher motivation* (pp. 22–54). Cambridge University Press.
- Han, J., & Yin, H. (2016). Teacher motivation: Definition, research development and implications for teachers. *Cogent Education*, 3(1), 12-23
- Ibok, E. E. & Unoh, E. O. (2019). Students' perception of teachers' evaluation technique and teacher-student relationship and their academic achievement in algebraic processes in Uyo Education Zone of Akwa Ibom, Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Science Education (IJ-SED)*, 1(1), 120-132.
- Ibok, E.E, Thomas, E. S, & Nyong, N. E.(2019). Influence of Gender and Achievement Motivation on Primary five Pupils' Multiplicative Thinking in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. *Prestige Journal of Education*. 2(2), 66-76.
- Ibok, E. E, Meremikwu A. N, Orim R. E., Anditung P. A, & Inah L. I. (2022) Does birth order or gender influence students' attitude toward mathematics in junior secondary schools in Eket Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria? *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 22(1)37-43
- Ibok, E. E., Meremikwu, A. N. & Umoh, S. S. (2020). Influence of students' religiosity on their academic achievement in Mathematics in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River state, Nigeria. *Prestige journal of counselling psychology*, 3 (2), 127-137
- Ibok, E. E. & Unoh, E. O. (2019). Students' perception of teachers' evaluation technique and teacher-student relationship and their academic achievement in algebraic processes in Uyo Education Zone of Akwa Ibom, Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Science Education (IJ-SED)*, 1(1), 120-132.
- Klassen, R. M., Al-Dhafri, S., Hannok, W., & Betts, S. M. (2011). Investigating pre-service teacher motivation across cultures using the Teachers' Ten Statements Test. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27(3), 579 - 588.
- McLean, L., Taylor, M., & Jimenez, M. (2019). Career choice motivations in teacher training as predictors of burnout and career optimism in the first year of teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85(1), 204 - 214.
- Müller, K., Alliata, R., & Benninghoff, F. (2009). Attracting and retaining teachers: A question of motivation. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 37(5), 574–599.
- Muñoz-Fernández, G. A., Rodríguez Gutiérrez, P., & Luque Vilchez, M. (2019). Initial teacher training for secondary education in Spain: Profile and motivations of the future teaching staff. *Journal of educación*, 22(1), 71–92
- Parr, A., Gladstone, J., Rosenzweig, E., & Wang, M.-T. (2021). Why do I teach? A mixed-methods study of in-service teachers' motivations, autonomy-supportive instruction, and emotions. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 98, 10-23
- Stolk, J. D., Gross, M. D., & Zastavker, Y. V. (2021). Motivation, pedagogy, and gender: Examining the multifaceted and dynamic situational responses of women and men in college STEM courses. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 8, 35(4),67-77
- Struyven, K., Jacobs, K., & Dochy, F. (2013). Why do they want to teach? The multiple reasons of different groups of students for undertaking teacher education. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 28(3), 1007–1022.
- Tardif, M., & Tremblay-Gagnon, D. (2021). Teaching today: From career choice to the first years in the profession. http://www.pum.umontreal.ca/catalogue/enseigner_aujourd'hui
- Watt, H. M., & Richardson, P. W. (2017). Motivational factors influencing teaching as a career choice: Development and validation of the FIT-Choice Scale. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 75(3), 167–202.
- Watt, H. M., & Richardson, P. W. (2020). An introduction to teaching motivations in different countries: Comparisons using the FIT-Choice Scale. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(3), 185–197.
- Watt, H. M., & Richardson, P. W. (2020). Motivation of higher education faculty: (How) it matters. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 100, 116-123.